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CSS study protocol defined and ethics approval received

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1. Introduction

This milestone is part of Task 2.1 involving the development of a harmonized monitoring plan to assess PPP distribution and related ecosystem, plant, animal, and human (EPAH) health in 11 CSS. It is primarily based on the WP2 monitoring plan (D2.1) that ensures the harmonisation of sampling, storage, and field and laboratory analyses, but also on WP3 activities (e.g. model development and verification, duplicate portion analysis). The field study protocol applies to all 2021 CSS activities. In order to interpret the results of field samples, it is necessary to cross-check the data collected with the information provided by the main actors involved. This will be achieved by following a multi-actor approach that brings together a wide range of stakeholders from local to international level through workshops and interviews. These workshops and interviews are designed to collect additional information in order to support the empirical knowledge in the field and ensure the applicability of our findings.

Since detailed protocol on the methods used is already given in D2.1 (Monitoring Protocol, M6 – a document to be used mostly by CSS teams), the main objectives of this Milestone are (i) to present a summary of the standardized methods used for sampling, storage, and field and laboratory analyses (for peers and stakeholders information mostly); (ii) an overview of the CSS questionnaires on farm management, PPP applications, and ecosystem, livestock and human health (again, for peers and stakeholders information mostly), and (iii) compilation of ethical approvals necessary for human sampling (documents also required for EC verification). Our purpose is to follow a multi-actor approach that brings together a wide range of stakeholders from local to international level to achieve the overall goal of the SPRINT project.

With, two specific objectives of direct interest to the current report and field study protocol:

- Assess PPP component mixtures and distribution in the environment (soil, water, air, non-target organisms), plants (crops), animals (livestock) and humans (farmers, non-farmer residents and consumers), and related health state of organisms and humans, in 11 case study sites (CSS), covering conventional and organic farm systems.

- Estimate direct and indirect PPP component exposure levels for selected non-target organisms, plants, farm animals and humans in the CSS, using existing and new data, advanced models that aim to unravel transport pathways of PPP residues (components and metabolites) across environmental domains, and intake mechanisms of different organisms and humans, including corresponding food and feeding patterns. These data will be used for the improvement of fate/exposure models.

1.1 Overview on the sampling design

The general information collected at the CSS covers the natural and human context, farms, field and crop characteristics. **Figure 1** compiles the not-target organisms and matrices to be analysed per sample for the Environment (top), Livestock (middle), and Human (bottom). For more details on the matrices used for the pesticide analysis, refer to section 4.1.

Figure 1. Parameters overview per environment, animal, and human related samples.

1.2 Choice of the sampling period

All samples and most field data will be collected in 2021, in the growing season. The exact timing of the sample collection depends on the growing season of crops of interest in a particular CSS. The middle of the growing season was selected to be relevant with regard to the level of the PPP use (target 50 – 80% of PPP applied) and is also a good period to study impacts on non-target species. The study includes conventional (or integrated) and organic farm systems in each CSS region.

2. STUDY LOCATIONS AND IMPORTANCE OF THE CROP CONSIDERED

The selection of crops and locations serves the overall goal of covering a number of climate zones and main crop types across Europe and Argentina (Table 1). CSS cover also the three EU PPP regulatory zones: Northern Europe (CSS 9, 10), Central Europe (CSS 3, 4, 7) and Southern Europe (CSS 1, 2, 5, 6 and 8). Argentina was considered in the study to include the remote use of PPP that is an important part of EU conventional agriculture practices regarding livestock -i.e. via the import of soya in feed. Additional information on the reasoning of selected CSS regions and crops is provided in **Table 1**. CSS2 and CSS9 will be used as reference sites for additional sample collection (over one year dust and air sampling by active samplers, and dust sampling by wind erosion using passive samplers).

Table 1. Plant sampling per CSS according to the crop under consideration.

CSS N° / climate	Crop type	Plant	Usage	Additional information (production/surface area, PPP use).
CSS1-SP Semiarid Mediterranean	Vegetables	Broccoli	Food	The value of fresh vegetables produced in the EU was EUR 34.5 billion in 2017 ^{1a} . 41% of EU vegetable samples analysed had pesticide residues; in 3.5% of the vegetables, those residues exceed the authorised limits ^{1c} .
CSS2-PT Mediterranean with oceanic influence	Vineyards	Grape	Wine	The total area under vines in the EU was 3.2 million ha in 2015, representing 1.8 % of the total utilised agricultural area ^{2a} . Quantifiable pesticide residues were observed in more than 86% of grapes ^{2b} . The Pesticide Action Network PAN Europe tested 40 different red wines - from countries that included Germany, France

				and Italy - and found that 35 of them contained traces of pesticide ^{2c} .
CSS3-FR Atlantic	Vineyards	Grape	Wine	See CSS2 remarks.
CSS4-CH Continental	Orchards	Mainly apples	Food	Orchards production of fruits trees in Europe occupies an area of 1'309 000 ha ^{2a} . The European parliament reported that in 73% of the fruit samples tested, pesticide residues were observed, and in 2.7% of the fruit those residues exceeded the authorised limits ^{4b} . In all samples tested (36 for water and 49 for soil), 53 different pesticides were found, while 78 percent of soil samples and 72 percent of water samples contained residues of at least one type of pesticides. ^{4c}
CSS5-IT Humid continental climate to humid subtropical	Vegetables	to be determined	Food	See CSS1 remarks.
CSS6-HR Mediterranean / Submediterranean	Olives	Olives	Food	The EU is worldwide the largest producer of olive oil, accounting for 69% of the world production. In the EU, there are nine producing Member States: Spain, Italy, Greece, Portugal, France, Slovenia, Croatia, Cyprus and Malta. They account for a total of around 5 million hectares of olive groves ^{3a} . Although high levels of pesticide residues are usually low in olive oil, 0.6% of the EU samples tested olive oils on the European market contained pesticide residues above the allowed limits ^{6b}
CSS7-SI Moderate continental and sub-alpine humid climate	Maize	Maize	Food	The cropping area within the 27 EU member states = 8.3 million ha for grain maize and 5.0 million ha for silage maize (2007 data) ⁷ .
CSS8-CR Mixture of temperate continental and oceanic	Oil plants	Sunflower, poppy, oilseed rape, mustard	Seeds for oil and food, seed	The EU cultivates three types of oilseed crop; the main two are rape and turnip rape, and sunflower. The EU harvested an estimated 29.5 million tonnes of oilseeds in 2019. Organochloride pesticide residues were found at particularly high concentrations in oil plants ⁸ .
CSS9-NL Humid Atlantic	Potatoes	Potatoes	Seed	The EU produced 51.2 million tonnes of potatoes in 2019. 35 pesticide residues were found in potatoes ^{9a} . At the EU level, 41.8% of the potatoes analysed contained

				quantified residues at or below the maximum residue levels ^{9b} .
CSS10–DK Borea, Atlantic and continental influence	Cereals	Winter wheat, spring and winter barley, winter rye, oats	Food and animal feed/fodder	The total cereal production in Europe amounted to 245.2 million ton with the highest reported consumption equal to 12 g/kg bw/day. Intake of pesticide residues from cereals was estimated to 18 µg/day/person in 2007. The estimated intake from cereals accounted for 21% of the estimated total intake of pesticide residues from food and beverages which was 83 µg/day ¹⁰ .
CSS11–AR Template – Sub-humid	Leguminous	Soya	feed	Most soya comes from the Americas and nearly half from just two countries, Brazil and Argentina. Pesticide, in particular glyphosate based herbicides, use has reportedly gone up from 35 million litres in 1990 to 285 million in 2009, due largely to the huge increases in GM soybean farming covering approximately 22 million hectares over many regions of the country. Glyphosate spraying went from less than 2 litres per hectare in 1996 to 20 litres per hectare in 2010, most likely due to the development of resistance to the herbicide ¹¹ .

^{1a}[https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=The fruit and vegetable sector in the EU - a statistical overview](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=The_fruit_and_vegetable_sector_in_the_EU_-_a_statistical_overview)

^{1b}https://www.pan-europe.info/sites/pan-europe.info/files/Pesticide%20Residues%20in%20EU%20food%20PR%20PAN%20Europe%2004072019_Final%20%281%29.pdf

^{1c}https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document//E-8-2018-001387_EN.html

^{1d}[https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Vineyards in the EU - statistics&oldid=397227](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Vineyards_in_the_EU_-_statistics&oldid=397227)

^{2a}[https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Vineyards in the EU - statistics&oldid=397227](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Vineyards_in_the_EU_-_statistics&oldid=397227)

^{2b}Schusterova, D.; Hajslova, J.; Kocourek, V.; Pulkrabova, J. Pesticide Residues and Their Metabolites in Grapes and Wines from Conventional and Organic Farming System. *Foods* **2021**, *10*, 307. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods10020307>

^{2c}<https://www.dw.com/en/european-wines-contaminated-with-pesticide-study-shows/a-3220424>

^{4a}[https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=File:Production area of fruit trees, EU, 2017 \(ha\).png](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=File:Production_area_of_fruit_trees,_EU,_2017_(ha).png)

^{4b}https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document//E-8-2018-001387_EN.html

^{4c}<https://www.lifegate.com/apple-orchards-pesticides-greenpeace>

^{6a}https://ec.europa.eu/info/news/producing-69-worlds-production-eu-largest-producer-olive-oil-2020-feb-04_en

^{6b}<https://www.cbi.eu/market-information/processed-fruit-vegetables-edible-nuts/olive-oil/market-entry>

⁷<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1111/j.1439-0418.2009.01491.x>

⁸https://www.researchgate.net/publication/51400635_Organochlorine_pesticide_residues_in_4_types_of_vegetable_oils

^{9a}Tri Thanh Nguyen, Carmen Rosello, Richard Bélanger, Cristina Ratti. Fate of Residual Pesticides in Fruit and Vegetable Waste (FVW) Processing. *Foods* **2020**, *9*, 1468; doi:10.3390/foods9101468

^{9b}<https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.2903/j.efsa.2019.5743>

¹⁰https://www.eurl-pesticides.eu/library/docs/cf/Cereals%20and%20feedingstuff%202009%204_.pdf

¹¹https://www.i-sis.org.uk/Pesticide_illnesses_and_GM_soya.php

3. SAMPLING OF ECOSYSTEM, ANIMALS, AND HUMANS

The study design includes populations of various species that are considered recipients of pesticides exposures in their own living environment: farm animals, humans and non-target species. All of these populations may be found in and around farm buildings but also on the fields around the farm. In addition, the study design aims to capture the species that were not intended to be exposed, hence non-target species. For humans it is planned to divide the study populations into three subpopulations that cover different exposure settings. Below each of the populations and subpopulations will be discussed in more detail.

An overview of monitoring environment, livestock including sheep, goat, dairy, cattle for meat and pig (the distribution of animal types per CSS is given in section 4.7), and human to assess in situ health and laboratory data is presented in below. **Table 2** compiles the type and number of samples to collect per farming system and per CSS. These samples will be used to assess both PPP distribution and health in Environment, Livestock and Human. For more details on the matrices used for the pesticide analysis, refer to section 4.1.

Table 2. Type and number of Environment (A), Livestock (B) and Human (C) related samples per CSS; number depends on the existing individuals per CSS.

A) Environment

FS	Soil	Water	Sedi ment	Dust outsi de/ air	Dust indoor	Plant	Earth wor ms	Benthic macro- invertebra te	Fish	Bat (faeces)	Soil dwelling insects	Flying insects
C/I	10	6	6	1	6-10	10	10	3	6	5	15	15
O	10			1	6-10	10	10				15	15

B) Livestock – Sheep, goat, dairy, cattle meat & pig

FS	urine	faeces	blood	wristbands	milk	feed	faeces	blood	wristbands
C/I	18	18	18	6	6	6	2	2	2
O	18	18	18	6	6	6	2	2	2

C) Human

F S	urine			faeces			blood			wristbands			Nasal		
	Farm ers	Ru ral	Consu mer	Farm ers	Ru ral	Consu mer	Farm ers	Ru ral	Consu mer	Farm ers	Ru ral	Consu mer	Farm ers	Ru ral	Consu mer
C/I	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12
O	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12

3.1 Humans

The study design focuses on specific locations of farms. Taking these locations as a reference human participants are recruited to try and capture a range of different exposure scenarios that cover those defined by EFSA (EFSA 2014) of which some study participants may be directly exposed and close to the application, whereas others may be living further away from the fields where pesticides are applied and receive exposure e.g. via drift, air, dust. Two exposure patterns are currently used in exposure modelling of pesticide exposure: consumer and bystander. The consumer is well covered in **3.1.3** but the bystander situation can occur for different individuals. The bystander is defined as a person at the perimeter of a field where pesticides are applied (EFSA, 2014). In the context of our study this could be residents, i.e. the farmer and additional household members of what we would like to refer to as 'farmer family'. The farmer can be an operator or worker (EFSA, 2014). In addition, this could also be another type of rural resident with no professional involvement in farming, referred to as the non-farmer resident who form a household and are referred to as 'non-farmer families' if their property is next to agricultural land where pesticides are being applied (**3.1.2**). Both members of non-farmer families and consumers could also be bystanders when commuting, recreating or otherwise coming close to agricultural land where pesticides are being applied. This is likely to occur if the field of pesticide application is adjoining to public spaces such as a road or recreational area. In this study, we include the three categories of populations exposed directly or indirectly to pesticides with a representative number of each category (**Table 2**).

3.1.1 Farmer families

The farmer is the central person involved directly in the planning of PPP use and decisions when and how the products are used. The farmer may apply pesticides and receive occupational exposure. In some cases the pesticide application may be conducted by a contractor. As farmers are often living on or near the farmland the farmer and farmer family is an interesting target population and known to receive a higher exposure compared to other non-farmer families living in a rural environment (Figueiredo et al., 2021). Both farmers and non-farmer families are part of the wider community described as consumers in a region where the CSS data are collected. There is an overlap in background exposure from the environment, e.g. by pesticides not used in that region. Obviously, the consumption of agricultural products is a potential source of pesticide residues that may be locally produced, imported from EU member states or to some extent also related to products imported from outside of the EU.

3.1.2 Neighbours non-farmer families

The non-farmer families are defined as the rural inhabitants in the neighbourhood of the farmland where pesticides are applied. These families may be direct neighbours of farmer families but their residences may also be at close range of fields where pesticides are applied. Members of these families may be exposed directly by spray drift when they are outside during spray applications. Pesticides may also disperse in the gas phase or by airborne dust that penetrates into the residence (Oerlemans et al, 2021). Environmental exposures are then defined as 'rural background' and depend on the type of crop and type of farm systems in the region. Tracking is another described mechanism by which pesticides may be translocated into the home environment (Tang et al., 2018). Some farmer families may also buy local products from neighbouring farms which means that in an organic farm system these products may have no detectable or low pesticide residues.

3.1.3 Consumers

The consumer is the reference for persons who are exposed to a background environmental exposure. The average consumer is expected to receive most of the exposure through the diet. The pesticide residue mixture is

dependent on the composition of their 'market basket' that may consist of local products (see non-farmer families) but also products bought from a grocery or supermarket and may include products imported from EU member states and also from products from outside the EU.

3.2 Farm animals

Animals come into contact with pesticides in many ways. Pesticide poisoning in animals is usually due to misuse or accidental exposure (Wang et al., 2006). Livestock may be exposed to pesticides from direct application, applications to barns and pastures, or drift from nearby agricultural crops of fodder.

All pesticides have some level of toxicity. Even the least-toxic products can cause health problems if an animal is exposed to enough of it. The risk of health problems depends not only on how toxic the ingredients are, but also on the amount of exposure to the product.

3.3 Non-target species

Non-target or residual pesticide toxicity would also disrupt the population of some of the valuable soil invertebrates like earthworms, predatory centipedes and carabid beetles. Accumulation of pesticides in resistant or tolerant species may provoke episodes of toxicity to organisms higher in the food chain. Recent studies suggest that several non-target organisms, from bees to mammals, show a wide variety of toxic effects of pesticides exposure, including impaired behaviour, development and reproduction (Alengebawy et al., 2021). Among mammals, bats are usually a neglected taxon among ecotoxicological studies, although they play important ecological and economical roles in forest ecosystems and agriculture through to seed dispersal and insect population control (Oliveira et al., 2021). Thus, our study focuses on terrestrial non-target living on the farmland and in its vicinity such as earthworms, soil dwelling insects, flying insects and specially bees and bats. For the aquatic species we selected fish and aquatic benthic macroinvertebrates.

4. STUDY OUTCOMES

4.1 General overview

EPAH health is assessed in the 11 CSS based on the key parameters: PPP, microbiome, diversity and other health indicators. **Table 3** shows an overview of the parameters assessed in each CSS.

Table 3. Overview of the parameters assessed in the environment, livestock and human matrices.

	Matrix	Health state
Environment	Soil	PPP analyses, soil microbiome, SOM, C _{min} , N _{min} , PLFA analyses, enzyme activities, functional gene analyses
	Water and water sediment	PPP analysis
		SOM, granulometry and PPP analyses, Benthic macro-invertebrates for diversity assessment
	Indoor and outdoor dust	PPP analysis
	Plant	Yield data, pest incidence, weed infestation (questionnaire), diseases, and PPP analysis
	Earthworm	PPP analysis, earthworm diversity, Earthworm gut microbiome
	Fish (faeces, fillet and liver)	PPP analysis, gut microbiome
	Bats (faeces)	Bat diversity, PPP and gut microbiome
Insects (flying and ground dwelling)	Biodiversity	
Livestock*	Urine	PPP and clinical parameters/biomarkers
	faeces	PPP and microbiome analysis
	blood	PPP and clinical parameters/biomarkers
	wristbands	PPP assessment
	milk (if applicable)	PPP analysis
	Feed	PPP analysis
	-	Reproductivity and diseases (questionnaire)
Human	urine	PPP and clinical parameters/biomarkers analysis
	faeces	PPP and microbiome analysis
	blood	PPP and clinical parameters/biomarkers analysis
	Wristbands	PPP assessment
	Nasal swabs	Microbiome
	-	Reproductivity and diseases (questionnaire)

*valid also for chicken and cats

4.2 Abiotic and Biotic environment

Five abiotic matrices and seven biotic matrices will be collected each CSS. Abiotic composite samples include soil, water, outdoor air/dust, indoor dust, and aquatic sediment. Biotic matrices including plant/crops, earthworms, fish, bats, insects and macro-invertebrates will be collected in all CSS and analysed for diversity (earthworms, benthic macroinvertebrates, and insects), PPPs content (plant/crop, earthworms, fish and bat faeces) and microbiome (earthworms, fish, bat faeces). Shortly after sampling, the

collected matrices will be stored deep frozen (-20°), except for earthworms used for diversity assessment and insects that will be stored in a 70% alcohol solution (**see Table 4**).

Table 4. Conditions of sampling and storage of environment components.

System	Sample amount	sampling design	Storage conditions
Soil	2 Kg	0 – 5 cm deep or 0-20 cm deep	4°C for FQ, Cmin, Nmin/-20°C for PPP and microbiome, PLFA, enzyme activities, and functional gene analyses
Water	2 L	sub-superficially	4°C or -20°C for longer period
Sediment	0.5 kg	0 – 10 cm deep	4°C and -20°C for longer period / Ethanol 70% v/v
Outdoor air/dust	not applicable (use of filter in TIEM devices, passive samplers)	150 cm height	-20°C
Indoor dust	100 gr	/	4°C or -20°C for longer period
Plant/crop	200 g	/	4°C and or -20°C
Earthworm	Collection*	25*25*25 cm monoliths	Part Preserved at 70% alcohol, part frozen
Fish	5 fishes	/	-20C
Bat	10-25 grams	/	-20°C
Ground-dwelling Insects	Collection*	120 pitfall traps in 100m ² , 3 measurements in time	70% ethanol
Flying insects	Collection*	1 transect/field, 150 m, 3 measurements in time	70% ethanol
Macro-invertebrates	Collection*	Net (1 mm - 500 µm mesh)	70% ethanol

*Collection of species found per CSS

4.3 Data needs for fate modelling

The general site and monitoring information will be used for analytical interpretation and as input parameters in WP3 exposure models. Additional air and outdoor dust samples will be collected with active samplers in two reference CSS (NL and PT) in order to improve develop a new model component on wind erosion. The health data and PPP distribution data from CSS will be used as input data for (eco)toxicological tests in WP4. The questionnaire data will also serve as basis for some WP6, WP7 and WP8 activities with the aim to assess direct and indirect exposures to PPP mixtures relevant to EPAH health by integrating existing data with new data obtained from CSS and come up with innovative exposure assessment models.

PPPs fate in soil, crops, surface water and air will be assessed by use of existing and under development of mathematical models. In particular, FOCUS PRZM (Pesticide Root Zone Model) and PEARL (Pesticide Emission Assessment at Regional and Local scales) models will be used to assess the fate of a PPP and relevant transformation products in the soil-plant system. PRZM calculates also run-off from treated fields to adjacent surface water bodies, which is then used by FOCUS TOXSWA (TOXic substances in Surface Waters) to assess PPPs concentrations in sediment and surface water. PPPs atmospheric concentration and dry deposition at multiple receptors around the treated field will be computed by OPS (Operational Atmospheric Transport Model for Priority Substances) dispersion model. Emissions due to volatilisation from soils are calculated by PEARL. A combination of PEARL-OPS is available in BROWSE software. Wind erosion potential, total soil discharged and total soil loss, to be used by OPS, will be computed by an underdevelopment module. Input data needed are meteorological data, data on physicochemical properties, PPP application data, field size and receptors configuration data. The data needed for the validation/verification of models performance are soil loss data and data on PPPs concentrations in the environmental matrixes considered in the assessment.

Overview on the input data for modelling are provided below:

- **Meteorological data** (e.g. Temperature, rainfall, wind speed and direction, evapotranspiration, solar radiation, air).

- **Air** (e.g. total suspended particles, wind erosion rate, PPP concentration in gaseous and particular phases).
- **Soil** (e.g. soil texture, SOM, hydraulic properties "measured or derived from maps).
- **Crop** (e.g. Scale used to identify the phenological development stages of a range of crop species "BBCH", leaf index area, crop height).
- **Surface water body** (e.g. size, depth, water flow, distance from field, SOC of the sediment)
- **Agronomic practices** (e.g. tillage, planting time, harvesting time, type of irrigation, pesticides application, dose, product, volume).

4.4 Human Exposure Modelling

- **Human specific input** (e.g., age, sex, weight, Height, time spent indoors, farmer/neighbor/consumer).
- **General & CSS specific input** (e.g., season of sampling, output from the environmental modelling to be used in the human exposure assessment, estimates of PPP concentration in different food items, daily lifestyle: how much time did the actor spend at home, use of pesticides at home, etc.).

4.5 Biomarker selection

After uptake, PPP components are metabolized which leads to internal exposure to metabolites. The cocktail of aforementioned PPP components and their secondary products may be absorbed via different routes of exposure. This uptake triggers a range of responses. Based on a review of the literature, we have pre-selected biomarkers that we consider relevant for the potential health impact. They include the following classes of biomarkers:

- a) Exposure biomarkers: PPP components and their degradation products and metabolites.
- b) Biochemical effect biomarkers: biomarkers that reflect a response to PPP components.

Both biomarker classes will be discussed in more detail below.

4.5.1 Exposure biomarkers

As biomarkers of exposure, we will use the active ingredients of PPPs or their metabolites or degradation products. If possible, we will also target

known co-formulants if relevant. The *a priori* selection of these analytes is described in **Table 5**. These substances will be analysed from different biological matrices such as blood and urine from farm animals (see 4.7) and human participants (see 4.8). Results of these exposure biomarker analyses can be compared with environmental samples collected on an individual basis (e.g. diffusive samples like wristbands) and samples collected in the micro-environment (e.g. homes of human subgroups). If the timeframe is well chosen this can lead to inferences regarding the potential source and route of exposures (Oerlemans et al., 2021).

4.5.2 Biochemical effect biomarkers

Biomarkers are applied in population-based studies to find support for involvement of certain molecular or cellular mechanisms to explain adverse effects. However, none of these biomarkers can be used to reflect disease prevalence directly and, in this study, we will not be collecting data on the occurrence of disease. We include biomarkers of possible value to study associations between exposure and health risk in future large scale epidemiological studies. A justification for the use of the listed biomarkers can be found in **Table 5**. The biomarkers can also be used in study populations of limited size and may result in inferences regarding predictors for future outcome related to certain exposure. The evidence to support associations between exposure and predictors of effect will be explored in WP2 and WP3 of the SPRINT project.

Table 5. Overview of the use of biomarkers to explore the associations of with pesticide exposures and specific health outcomes

Health outcomes	Biomarkers	Species	Study type	Reference
Immune system/ inflammatory status	hsCRP, IL-1 β , IL-2, IL-4, IL-5, IL-6, IL-8, IL-10, IL-13 and TNF- α , blood cell counts; SAA, VCAM-1 and ICAM-1	Human/rat/mouse	Population-based/controlled exposure	Colosio et al. 1999; Lee and Choi, 2002; Corsini et al. 2008
Kidney	KID1, NAG, urinary electrolytes, creatinine, and urinary proteins (OBS)	Human	Population-based	Valcke et al., 2017
Reprotoxic and developmental outcomes	DHEAS, FSH, GGT, LH, s-DHEA, SHBG,	Human	Population-based	Bretveld et al., 2006

	testosterone, estradiol, progesterone and cortisol			
Liver	ALT, AST, GGT and protein electrophoresis	Human/rat/mouse	Population-based/controlled exposure	Karami-Mohajeri et al. 2017
Neurotoxicity	AChE	Human	Population-based	Assis et al., 2018; Storm et al., 2000
	BChE	Human	Population-based	Lockridge and Masson P (2000)
	GFAP	Rat	Controlled exposure	Garcia et al., 2002
Thyroid	ft4, T3, T4 and TSH	Human/rat/mouse	Population-based/controlled exposure	Leemans et al., 2019; Campos and Freire, 2016
Metabolome	Metabolomics	Mouse	Controlled exposure	Wang and Wu 2015; Mol et al., 2016
Exposome	Exposomics	Human	Population-based	Jobst et al., 2013; Cariou et al., 2016
Microbiome	Gut and nose microflora	Mouse	Controlled exposure	Yuan et al., 2019

4.6 EPAH health status information using questionnaires

Laboratory analysis of PPP and related components (e.g. microbiome and diversity) is corroborated by a qualitative health status assessment based on interviews (see link given in the legend of **Table 6**).

In this study, we plan to conduct 6 questionnaires with the main stakeholders (i.e. farmers, neighbors, and consumers) (**Table 6**). For more details, refer to the monitoring plan (<https://sprint-h2020.eu/>).

Table 6. Overview of the CSS SPRINT questionnaires including links with the different project tasks.

WP	Time period	Description	Task	Will feed into
Questionnaire i				
2	At same time of sampling campaign	Collection of data to support an integrated risk management tool	Task 2.2 / D2.2(M12)	WP3, WP4, WP6
	At same time of sampling campaign	Monitoring pest and disease pressure on plants (crops) through interviews with farmers	Task 2.1	WP3, WP4
	At same time of sampling campaign	Information about overall health status from semi quantitative interviews	Task 2.1	WP3, WP4
Questionnaire ii				

7	At same time of sampling campaign	Attitude towards PPP	Task 7.1-	WP7
8		Communication	Task 8.2 -	WP8
Questionnaire iii				
2	At same time of sampling campaign	Natural and human environment	Task 6.1 - 6.3	WP2, WP6
		Farm characterization Field characterization Log book of the crop Pesticide record Fertilizer record Cost and benefits		
6	6 months after sampling campaign	Log book of the crop Pesticide record Fertilizer record Cost and benefits		
Questionnaire IV				
2	At same time of sampling campaign	Farmers/veterinaries will be interviewed regarding their perception of animal health and diseases occurring in the	Task 2.1	WP3, WP4
Questionnaire V				
2	At same time of sampling campaign	Designed to farmers, neighbors, and consumers regarding food intake 24 hours prior to their blood sample	Task 2.1	WP3, WP4
Questionnaire VI				
2	At same time of	To farmers only	Task 2.1	WP3, WP4, WP5

The questionnaires can be downloaded following the link below:

<https://sprint-h2020.eu/index.php/project-documents/registered-users/monitoring-plan-documents>

4.6.1 Humans

At the day of the blood and urine sampling, we conduct an interview with questions about exposure and general health for farmers, neighbours, and consumers. The questionnaire includes information on demographics, health, food, home environment, working conditions, the use of PPP and personal protective equipment. The complete questionnaire is available upon request.

4.6.2 Animals

The livestock questionnaire, specific to farmers, covers information on (i) existing livestock at the farm, (ii) husbandry (i.e. livestock existing at the own farm or at the adjacent farm, feed origin, type of feed, occurrence and manifestation of diseases), (iii) deficiency in immunological system,

malformations in new-borns, pneumonia, parasites, number of abortions, mastitis, and health problems in the last 5 years, and (iv) the use of medication and antibiotics. The complete questionnaire is available upon request.

4.6.3 Agronomic practices and economic data

A comprehensive questionnaire was designed to collect information about current agronomic practices and pesticide use at farm level across case study sites. Farmers will be interviewed before the crop season and again after harvest to identify any gaps between anticipated and actual practices, and related reasons for adapting planned practices as a function of e.g. pest pressure and environmental conditions. In addition to the natural and human environment, the questionnaire covers "farm characterization", "crop characterization", "fertilizer record", "pesticide record", and "cost and benefits".

The economic input-output data will also be instrumental for parameterising the farm-level simulation model in WP6. This is the basis for the ex-ante assessment of key pesticide use reduction strategies. In addition to clarify the current pesticide use practices, questionnaire data are used as input for a broader environmental sustainability assessment at farm level. Using all that data, we will be able to identify innovative strategies for reducing PPPs and going ahead with more sustainable agriculture. The complete questionnaire is available upon request.

4.6.4 Perceptions on pesticide use and transitions

To assist farmers in their decision-making towards a transition to the sustainable use of pesticides, data are captured through open questions on their knowledge and information needs. This includes identifying the main questions they would need answering when considering taking up a new practice and their preferred sources of information. The questionnaire contains information on (i) application levels of PPPs, (ii) main reasons for the current levels of pesticide application on the farm in the surrounding area, (iii) proposition to reduce pesticide applications in farming in general, and (iv) a more general question about the preferred format to receive information about SPRINT project. The complete questionnaire is available upon request.

4.6.5 24 hour food recall – from timing of blood sampling and the previous 24 hours

This short questionnaire should be completed 24 hour prior to blood sampling. In addition to the date and time, the CSS is requested to collect information on every food type, portion sizes, number of items (if applicable), beverages, and number of beverages for each of the meal types consumed by the participant the last 24 hours up to its timing of blood sampling. The complete questionnaire is available upon request.

4.6.6 Dust sampling questionnaire

This questionnaire is design to collect useful information to support indoor dust sampling. It contains the following information: (i) number of persons in the farmer households, (ii) date when the vacuum bag was placed and removed, (iii) vacuum cleaner model, (iv) Power of the vacuum cleaner engine, (v) vacuum cleaner setting used (minimum, medium, or maximum), (vi) frequency of the cleaning, and (vii) the area that has been cleaned. The complete questionnaire is available upon request.

4.7 Livestock and farm animals

PPPs may be ingested or absorbed by livestock following direct application of the product to the animal, through residues in feeding stuff, or as a result of treatment of their accommodation. Therefore, design of animal sampling follows the one established for human exposed in same way. However, slight differences still exist in terms of the amount of samples. In this study, a maximum of 36 animals should be selected per CSS depending on type of animal group (18 in organic and 18 in conventional farms, 3 animals/farm) (**Figure 1** and **Table 7**). The considered matrices and parameters are presented in **Table 8**.

Table 7. Distribution of Livestock distribution over the CSS

CSS n°	Country	Livestock type
1	Spain	Goat, rarely found in organic
2	Portugal	Chicken, pig
3	France	No livestock
4	Switzerland	Cows, chicken, sheep
5	Italy	No livestock
6	Croatia	Sheep
7	Slovenia	Cattle (6 farms, 18 cows), 4 cats
8	Chezh Republic	Cattle, sheep, chicken
9	Netherlands	Cattle (3)/sheep(1)/chicken(2)

10	Denmark	Cattle (12)
11	Argentina	Dairy, chicken

Table 8. Conditions of sampling and storage of livestock - sheep, goat, dairy, cattle for meat, & pig

Sample	Sampling amount	Sampling design	Storage conditions	Type of analysis
Urine	~100 ml urine/animal	3 animals / selected farm; 1 urine sample / animal	4 °C , and -18 after aliquitation	PPP and clinical parameters/biomarkers analyses
Faeces	~25 grams, 5 scoops/animal	same animals considered for urine collection.	18 °C)	PPP and microbiome
Blood	33mL/animal for bigger animals; 5ml in chicken (veterinarian).	same animals considered for urine collection.	store at -80 oC until shipment	PPP and clinical parameters/biomarkers
¹ Diffusive samplers	1/animal	same animals considered for urine and blood collection. use during 7 consecutive days	Store at -20°C	PPP analysis
Milk	50-100 ml	Either collected by the sampled animals OR from the milk container of the farm (whichever is possible)	Store in the freezer (-20C)	PPP analysis
Feed	500 gr	Feed = homegrown energy source (e.g. cereal/corn), homegrown protein source (e.g. rape seed/peas/beans), or roughage (hay, silage, pasture,)	storage in the fridge or ambient temperature (in the dark)	PPP analysis
Cat	4 cats/CSS; 2 from C and 2 from O farmer household Faeces:	1 faeces sample per cat 1 blood sample per cat 1 wristband per cat (Veterinarian for blood)	Store at -20°C	PPP, microbiome, and clinical parameters/biomarkers

¹The silicon wristband for human sampling was adapted for diffusive sampling purposes in animals. The measurement principle is the same as in humans. The human wristband is used as an ankle strap on the hind leg in cow and sheep. In goat and cat a smaller size silicon band is attached to a collar. In chicken barns it is recommended to hang the diffusive sampler on a fixed location from the

ceiling. Before silicon samplers can be used, they need to be cleaned thoroughly and tested on the instrument of final analysis. The wristband will be worn continuously prior to collection of urine and blood.

4.8 Human sample collection

Most pesticides are readily biotransformed and appear in **urine** as conjugated or free metabolites. Only a limited number of pesticides may appear in urine as a parent substance. In addition to urinary pesticides or metabolites, urine may contain a limited number of additional biomarkers (**Table 9**). **The blood** level of pesticides and their metabolites are primary study outcomes and will serve as input to BPK modelling of target dose for organs and organ systems where adverse effects may occur. Blood is the sample medium of preference of many additional biomarkers specified in **Table 9**. The **wristband** is a low-tech solution for personal passive sampling (O'Connell et al., 2014). The silicon material has the capability to absorb pesticides from the environment reflecting direct contact with environmental chemicals, either solid, liquid or gas phase and has been used before to study exposures to pesticides (Aerts, et al. 2018). We assess pesticide exposure through a safe and relatively new method: **silicone wristbands** (the famous Livestrong wristbands). Silicone bracelets are able to absorb pesticides from their surroundings. By analyzing both the wristbands and **nasal swabs**, we can determine with which pesticides the concerned participant had come in contact.

Table 9. Conditions of sampling and storage of human sampling; 72 participants will be involved (Farmers, rural, consumers) / CSS

Sample	Sampling amount	Sampling design	Storage conditions	Type of analysis
Urine	~58-125ml urine/participant	The urine sample will be collected directly after awakening and getting up (first morning void)	Store sample at approx. +4 °C in cool box powered by electricity	PPP and clinical parameters/biomarkers analysis
Faeces	5 tubes/ participant (4 empty tubes and one tube with stabilization buffer) 1 scoop per tube	The stool sample should be collected in the morning of the day the urine and blood collection	Immediately transfer to -18 °C and keep frozen	PPP and microbiome analysis
Blood	9 tubes (33mL)/participant	24h food recall form to be filled in by the participant (Questionnaire 5)	Store sample in cool box powered by electricity. Store at -80°C until shipment	PPP and clinical parameters/biomarkers analysis

Diffusive samplers	1 wristband/ participant used for 7 consecutive days.	The wristband is put on the participant during the week prior to the blood sampling	Store at -20°C until shipment	PPP analysis
Nasal swabs	1 nasal swab/ participant (left nostril)	Conducted by a laboratory technician	Store in cooling box (with ice packs)	Microbiome analysis

5. PPP COMPONENT SELECTION

In order to gain insight in (co)occurrence and fate of PPPs, environmental media and human and animal samples will be analysed for PPP components (active substances and degradation products/metabolites). For fate studies the most relevant pesticides to be measured will be those applied in the crops of the 11 CSSs shortly before the time of sampling. For hazard assessment, knowledge about occurrence of any (mixture of) pesticide(s) is relevant.

The EU Pesticides Database includes over 1400 active substances. Although only part of these is authorised, many can still be found in the environment or in food & feed and can therefore not *a priori* be ignored. Due to the high number and the wide variety in nature and physical chemical properties, it is inevitable that a selection has to be made for the substances to be included in the scope of the sample analysis for SPRINT. As a first restriction, only chemicals are considered, i.e. microbiological agents and plant extracts are excluded. In addition, inorganic substances, salts, attractants, complex mixtures (e.g., paraffin oils) and chemicals that obviously can be used for many other purposes than PPP are discarded, leaving a list of 873 chemical substances as a starting point for consideration. The selection process is summarized in **Figure 2** and will be explained below.

Figure 2. Selection of substances to be included in the analysis of environmental media, human and animal matrices. (a) data retrieved in October 2020. (b) preliminary numbers, compilation still in progress at the time of drafting this paper. (c) Excluded to bring the total number of substances down to approximately 200, amenable to multi-analyte methods. The reason for exclusion is indicated for each of the 9 selection criteria.

The selection for inclusion in SPRINT is based on two main selection criteria: *i*) known or expected use of PPP in the CSS (selection criteria 1-2 in **Figure 2**), *ii*) data on presence of pesticides (selection criteria 3-9 in **Figure 2**). Knowledge on which PPP will be used in the upcoming growing season is difficult to obtain at an early stage (1a and 1b in Figure 2). Therefore, as second best, a compilation was made of the pesticides authorised for the crops/country of each CSS.

Recent data on the presence of pesticides at the CSSs was hardly available. To fill this gap, before the actual monitoring study, a pre-screen exercise was done. This involved sampling in the CSSs region of dust from a farmer's premises (household dust and stable dust), soil from agricultural fields, and sediment from (nearby) water systems if available. Samples were taken between October 2020 and February 2021. The samples were screened for pesticides using LC and GC with full scan high resolution mass spectrometry (methods based on Zomer & Mol 2015, and Mol et al, 2016). Dust was

considered as an archive of pesticides covering a longer time window. The soil and sediment samples provided information on more persistent pesticides from the preceding season. The occurrence data was complemented with data available from the literature with focus on more generic EU wide monitoring data, and more recent sampling dates. Since SPRINT follows a 'OneHealth' approach, all sources were taken into account, both environmental, and food and feed. Example sources and papers include: Silva et al 2019, Geissen et al, 2021, and Riedo et al., 2021 for soil; Casado et al., 2019 for surface water; Hofmann et al., 2020 and Marlier et al., 2020 for air; EFSA 2020 for food; and WFSR 2021 and Mol et al., 2014 for feed materials.

Combining the data from all sources, the total number of pesticides that could be considered relevant for monitoring was almost 400. This was twice the number anticipated for inclusion in the SPRINT monitoring program, using LC-MS/MS and GC-MS/MS based multi-analyte methods. To reduce the number, for each of the selection criteria (except 1a, **Figure 2**), an exclusion criterion was set. These are indicated in **Figure 2**. This resulted in a short-list of 187 pesticides. From this list, pesticides not amenable to multi-analyte methods were excluded, with the exception of glyphosate and AMPA for which inclusion was already foreseen at the initiation of the project even though a separate analysis method is required for their analysis. Substances that are not (exclusively) pesticides (e.g. anthraquinone, DEET, triclosan) were also excluded from the scope. This results in a draft list of 150 pesticides, to which relevant degradation products and metabolites (as far as analytical standards are available and amenable to multi-analyte methods) will be added. Furthermore, once more details become known on actually applied PPP in the CSS, these may be added if not already included.

In order to obtain a consistent data set, and to allow linkage between the various sources and species, the same list of pesticides will be analysed in most of the samples, for all CSS. For the CSS in Argentina, additional pesticides may be added to address the local situation. For urine a different scope of analysis will apply. This is because most pesticides are not excreted as such, but as their phase I/II metabolites which are the biomarkers of exposure. Their determination is only possible if the main biomarker(s) are known, and the analytical reference standards available. For the selection

of biomarkers to be analysed in urine, the CSS monitoring data of the environmental samples will be taken into account.

6. ETHICS AND PRIVACY PROTECTION IMPLICATIONS

6.1 Ethics approval

The study will be conducted according to the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki (64th WMA General Assembly, Fortaleza, Brazil, October 2013). To support the submissions of applications to the ethics review boards in each of the 11 CSS, a generic description of the study protocol was prepared with standard solutions for participant information and informed consent. These documents were then translated and adapted to specific requirements in each country. Below the different aspects of ethics and GDPR will be discussed in more detail.

A version of study protocol was developed specifically for ethics approval. This protocol was dedicated to the recruitment of human participants and included details such as inclusion and exclusion criteria for participation, the contribution expected from study participants, and the potential benefits and burden for individual participants of joining the study.

A potential subject who meets any of the following criteria will be included in this study: both males and females 18 years or higher age on the day of recruitment. We will strive for a gender balance within all populations. Individuals who are not able to speak and/or read the local/regional/national language will be excluded from participation. **Table 10** provides an overview of the obtained ethics approvals for all CSS.

Table 10. Ethics applications and approvals by CSS number. See Annex 1 for the approval letters.

CSS	approval date	Committee
1	09-04-2021	Comité de Ética en la Investigación de la Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena
2	07-04-2021	Conselho de Ética e Deontologia - Universidade de Aveiro
3	09-04-2021	Le Comité de Protection des Personnes du Sud-Ouest et Outre-Mer 4
4	<i>Minor revisions submitted 15-05-2021</i>	<i>Swissethics, Bern, Switzerland – Expected date for final decision : 17.06.2021</i>
5	20-05-2021	Comitato Etico di Area Vasta Emilia Centro della Regione Emilia-Romagna
6	17-03-2021	Etičkog povjerenstva KBC-a Rijeka
7	12-05-2021	REPUBLIKA SLOVENIJA. MINISTRSTVO ZA ZDRAVJE. Komisija Republike Slovenije za medicinsko etiko
8	23-03-2021	ELSPAC Ethics Committee

9	01-03-2021	Commissie Mensgebonden Onderzoek Regio Arnhem-Nijmegen
10	29-04-2021	De Videnskabsetiske Komitéer For Region Midtjylland
11	27-05-2021	Comité de Ética de la Investigación Programa Temático Interdisciplinario en Bioética

All collected data will be pseudonymised before any treatment by replacing participant names with an ID code, and only some SPRINT researchers have access to these data.

The samples and data will be stored until the end of the project, period after which data and samples will be deleted and destroyed, respectively; environmental and biological samples (blood cell fractions, serum, plasma, urine, stool, nasal swabs) will be stored in -18 °C or -80 °C freezers depending on the type of specimen.

All data will be reported anonymously to protect the privacy of every subject. Person identifiable information will be kept in protected files until completion of this study. The handling of personal data complies with GDPR and the national legislation on data protection in the country where the CSS is planned

6.1.1 Participant information and informed consent

Every person who is invited to participate in the SPRINT study will receive a participant information brochure and an informed consent document, before he/she decides whether to participate or not.

6.2 Material and Data Transfer agreement (MDTA)

The material and associated data are supplied by the provider to the recipient subject to the terms and conditions of the SPRINT MDTA, and the SPRINT Data Policy, which control in the event of any discrepancy between the languages here and there.

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DATOS DEL INTERESADO

Nombre: ALCÓN PROVENCIO, FRANCISCO JOSÉ

Email: francisco.alcon@upct.es

Notificación

Conforme a lo establecido en los artículos 40 y siguientes de la Ley 39/2015, de 1 de octubre, del Procedimiento Administrativo Común de las Administraciones Públicas, esta Secretaría General pasa a notificarle lo siguiente:

Resolución favorable CEI21_002

REUNIDO

El 9 de abril de 2021 el Comité de Ética en la Investigación de la Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena para la evaluación ética de la actividad de I+D+i "Sustainable Plant Protection Transition: A global Health Approach (SPRINT)", presentada por D. Francisco José Alcón Provencio y D^a Josefina Contreras Gallego como responsables de dicha actividad, y con el fin de llevar a cabo las funciones propias del Comité promoviendo que las investigaciones realizadas se desarrollen cumpliendo los máximos estándares de rigor, honestidad y responsabilidad.

ACUERDA

PRIMERO. - INFORMAR FAVORABLEMENTE la realización de la actividad de I+D+i para la que se solicitó la evaluación del Comité de Ética en la Investigación por D. Francisco José Alcón Provencio y D^a Josefina Contreras Gallego, haciendo constar expresamente que la actividad deberá ejecutarse siguiendo estrictamente las instrucciones del Delegado de Protección de Datos Personales de la UPCT.

SEGUNDO. - Notificar el presente Acuerdo a D. Francisco José Alcón Provencio y a D^a Josefina Contreras Gallego.

Contra este Acuerdo se podrá interponer recurso de alzada ante el Rector en el plazo de 1 mes a contar desde el día siguiente de su notificación según lo dispuesto en el artículo 122 de la Ley 39/ 2015 de 1 de octubre del procedimiento administrativo común de las administraciones públicas.

En Cartagena, a 9 de abril de 2021

PRESIDENTA DEL COMITÉ DE ÉTICA EN LA INVESTIGACIÓN DE LA UPCT

(firmado electrónicamente)

Comissão Permanente para os Assuntos de Investigação (CPAI)

Parecer nº: 03-CED/2021

Requerente: Nelson José Cabaços Abrantes

Título do Projeto: “*SPRINT - Sustainable Plant Protection Transition: A Global Health Approach*”

Investigador responsável: Nelson José Cabaços Abrantes

Equipa de Investigação:

- Nelson José Cabaços Abrantes, Investigador Auxiliar, CESAM, Universidade de Aveiro.
- Fernando Gonçalves, Professor Associado com Agregação, CESAM, Departamento de Biologia, Universidade de Aveiro.
- Joana Pereira, Investigadora, CESAM, Universidade de Aveiro.
- Isabel Campos, Investigadora, CESAM, Universidade de Aveiro.

Enquadramento Institucional: CESAM, Universidade de Aveiro

Relatora: Ana Isabel Andrade

Relatores Adjuntos: António Rocha Andrade, Armando Pinho, Domingos Moreira Cardoso, Isabel Malaquias e Paula Cristina Moreira Silva Pereira.

I. Relatório

O principal objetivo deste projeto é desenvolver, testar, validar e fornecer um conjunto de Ferramentas de Avaliação de Risco de Saúde Global para a avaliação integrada dos impactos dos Pesticidas em ecossistemas terrestres e aquáticos, plantas, animais e saúde humana (EPAH). Mais concretamente pretende-se: avaliar a distribuição de resíduos de pesticidas e sua mistura no meio ambiente (solo, água, ar, organismos não-alvo), plantas (plantações), animais (gado) e humanos (agricultores, operadores, população rural, consumidores); avaliar os custos e benefícios do uso de pesticidas na agricultura; fornecer recomendações políticas e regulamentares inovadoras e desenvolver uma agenda de investigação sobre a questão.

O processo contém informação no que respeita a:

- Descrição dos objetivos do projeto e da metodologia a seguir, incidindo em agricultores, residentes rurais e consumidores;
- Descrição detalhada da metodologia, com indicação clara dos procedimentos e tipos de dados a recolher, bem como apresentação de protocolos a seguir na investigação;
- Indicação do investigador responsável e dos outros elementos da equipa;
- Enquadramento institucional e científico (projeto H2020 ID 862568 - Comissão Europeia; CESAM, Universidade de Aveiro).

Apêndices e Anexos:

- Declaração do encarregado de proteção de dados da Universidade de Aveiro;
- Tabela de Questões éticas associadas ao projeto;
- *Participant information for medical scientific research*;
- Generic research protocol - *Case Study Sites* (Protocolo de investigação, coordenação do projeto);
- *Portuguese SPRINT CSS leaflet*; *Portuguese SPRINT farmer brochure* – Folheto/documentos explicativos para participantes no estudo;
- *SPRINT Personal Interview Questionnaire*.
- *Certificate of Informed Consent*.
- Declaração de apoio por parte da coordenadora do CESAM.

II. Parecer**a. Fundamentação**

1. O pedido de parecer relativo ao projeto em causa apresenta-se bem elaborado e fundamentado, assinalando as questões éticas associadas ao seu desenvolvimento.
2. Os objetivos do estudo são claramente justificados, inserindo-se numa estratégia mais vasta de reduzir a dependência dos pesticidas, concebendo e implementando abordagens mais integradas para a sua utilização, procurando salvaguardar a competitividade da agricultura na EU e contribuindo para a saúde global
3. A metodologia assenta na constituição de Casos de Estudo (CSS), baseada num protocolo (SPRINT Protocole) harmonizado para todo o projeto europeu para garantir a comparabilidade entre os diferentes CSS na Europa.
4. O projeto recolherá dados vários (questionários a agricultores, residentes rurais e consumidores; amostras ambientais, humanas e animais). Todos os dados serão anonimizados e os participantes no estudo serão voluntários, dando o seu consentimento informado, livre e esclarecido.
5. Não está previsto nenhum impacto significativo na população amostrada decorrente da investigação em causa;
6. O projeto envolve o processamento de informação genética ou de dados pessoais (e.g. saúde, hábitos sexuais, etnicidade, opinião política, religiosa ou convicções filosóficas), mas todos os dados (e.g. saúde, hábitos alimentares) serão codificados.
7. O investigador responsável será o único a ter acesso às informações que ligam os participantes do estudo aos resultados do estudo. Para acesso a dados,

existirão acordos de transferência que serão assinados pelo remetente e pelo destinatário.

8. O projeto envolve investigação em animais (ensaios ecotoxicológicos com peixes expostos a misturas de pesticidas), comprometendo-se o requerente a pedir parecer ao Órgão Responsável pelo Bem Estar Animal (ORBEA), em fase mais adiantada de desenvolvimento do projeto.

De acordo com o exposto, conclui-se que o projeto em análise respeita os princípios de ética neste tipo de estudos, na medida em que assegura:

1. A participação dos indivíduos (agricultores, residentes não agrícolas e consumidores) de forma voluntária e com consentimento prévio;
2. A recolha de amostras biológicas humanas (sangue, urina, fezes, zaragatoas nasais) e de dados humanos (e.g. dados biométricos, de saúde, dieta), respeitando toda a privacidade dos participantes;
3. A solicitação de parecer ao Órgão Responsável pelo Bem Estar Animal (ORBEA), em fase mais adiantada de desenvolvimento do projeto.

b. Recomendações

1. Deverá sempre ser respeitado o Regulamento Geral de Proteção de Dados (RGPD), assim como a legislação Europeia relacionada com a investigação em seres humanos.
2. Deverá ser pedido Parecer ao Órgão Responsável pelo Bem Estar Animal (ORBEA), em tempo útil, e anterior, à realização da realização dos ensaios ecotoxicológicos.

Conclusão

De acordo com o anteriormente referido e com os princípios seguidos por este Conselho, é emitido o seguinte parecer:

1. A Comissão Permanente do Conselho de Ética, constituída pelos Relatores acima indicados, após apreciação da documentação recebida e atendendo a que os procedimentos descritos no projeto de investigação:
 - 1.1 Garantem que os participantes são previamente informados e esclarecidos sobre o estudo;
 - 1.2 Incluem o consentimento informado dos participantes;
 - 1.3 Garantem o anonimato dos dados recolhidos;
2. Considera que **merece parecer favorável** a realização do projeto “*SPRINT - Sustainable Plant Protection Transition: A Global Health Approach*”.

O Presidente da CPAI

I. Plenário CED

Submetido ao CED o respetivo parecer da sua Comissão Permanente, este Conselho, em sua reunião plenária de 7 de abril de 2021, por entender que ficam salvaguardadas as exigências éticas e os princípios da justiça e da autonomia e bem-estar dos participantes, concorda por unanimidade com o mesmo, em razão do que o ratifica e dá **parecer favorável** à realização do projeto intitulado: “*projeto “SPRINT - Sustainable Plant Protection Transition: A Global Health Approach”*”.

O Presidente do CED

COMITE DE PROTECTION DES PERSONNES DU SUD-OUEST ET OUTRE-MER 4

N°IRB : **IORG0009855**

Agréé par arrêté ministériel en date du 16 mai 2018

Constitué selon l'arrêté du 21 juin 2018 et modifié par l'arrêté du 23 février 2021

de l'Agence Régionale de Santé de la Nouvelle-Aquitaine

Cabanis Haut – Centre Hospitalier Esquirol – 15 rue du Docteur Raymond Marcland – BP 61730

87025 LIMOGES CEDEX

☎ : 05.55.43.11.19 - 📠 : 05.55.43.10.27 - 💻 : cpps004@ch-esquirol-limoges.fr

A Limoges, le 9 avril 2021

Réf. du présent avis ou délibération sous le N°: **21.01.28.68911 / CPP2021-02-019b / 2021-A00205-36**

Le Comité a été saisi par dépôt sur le SI de la CNRIPH, le 5 février 2021, d'une demande d'avis pour un projet de recherche mentionnée au 2° de l'article L1121-1 du code de la santé publique ne portant pas sur un produit mentionné à l'article L.5311-1 du CSP

Transition vers une protection durable des cultures : une approche de santé globale (SPRINT)

Le Comité a jugé ce dossier recevable le 7 février 2021.

dont le promoteur est

Université de Wageningen

Madame Violette GEISSEN

Droevendaalsesteeg 3

6708 KD WAGENINGEN

Pays Bas

dont le coordonnateur est

Professeur Isabelle BALDI

INSERM U1219 – Equipe EPICENE

Service Santé Travail Environnement

CHU de Bordeaux

146 rue Léo Saignat

33076 BORDEAUX

Réunion plénière dématérialisée du 11 mars 2021:

Catégorie I - Personnes qualifiées en matière de recherche biomédicale

Christine VALLEJO, Murielle GIRARD, Anne-Marie BRIL

Catégorie I - Personnes qualifiées en matière de biostatistique ou d'épidémiologie

Claire BAHANS

Catégorie II - Médecins généralistes

Philippe NICOT, Karen RUDELLE

Catégorie III – Pharmaciens

Marie-Anne de VINZELLES

Catégorie IV - Infirmier(e)s

Sèverine LALEU

Catégorie V - Personnes qualifiées en raison de leur compétence à l'égard des questions d'éthique

Dominique MALAUZAT

Catégorie VI – Psychologues

Sophie LEYMARIE

Catégorie VII - Travailleurs sociaux

Catégorie VIII - Personnes qualifiées en raison de leur compétence en matière juridique

Dominique JOUHANNEAUD, Pierre VERGNE, Paolo RASO

Catégorie IX - Représentants des associations agréées de malades et d'usagers du système de santé

Norbert VIDAL, Dominique FLOUCAUD

Experts pédiatres : Docteur Rachel FROGET – Professeur Vincent GUIGONIS – Docteur Alexandra MASSON-ROUCHAUD – Docteur Laure PONTHER

Les membres impliqués dans le projet n'ont pas participé à la délibération du 11 mars 2021.

Liste des documents étudiés:

Dossier administratif

Le courrier de demande d'avis daté et signé

Le formulaire daté et signé de demande d'autorisation auprès de l'ANSM ou de demande d'avis au comité de protection des personnes pour une recherche mentionnée au 1° ou au 2° de l'article L. 1121-1 du code de la sante publique ne portant pas sur un produit mentionné à l'article L. 5311-1 du code de la santé publique

Le document additionnel à la demande d'avis au CPP complété daté et signé

Dossier scientifique

Le protocole de recherche version 1.0 du 21/01/2021

Le résumé en français du protocole version 1.0 du 21/01/2021

Le document d'information et formulaire de consentement destiné aux patients version 1.0 du 21/01/2021

La copie de l'attestation d'assurance

L'attestation de l'adéquation des moyens humains, matériels et techniques au projet de recherche et de leur compatibilité avec les impératifs de sécurité des personnes qui s'y prêtent

La liste des centres version 1.0 du 21/01/2021 et *curriculum vitae* correspondant

Réunion plénière dématérialisée du 25 mars 2021 :

Catégorie I - Personnes qualifiées en matière de recherche biomédicale Christine VALLEJO, Anne-Marie BRIL

Catégorie I - Personnes qualifiées en matière de biostatistique ou d'épidémiologie Claire BAHANS, Cyrille CATALAN

Catégorie II - Médecins généralistes Philippe NICOT

Catégorie III - Pharmaciens Marie-Anne de VINZELLES

Catégorie IV - Infirmier(e)s Sèverine LALEU

Catégorie V - Personnes qualifiées en raison de leur compétence à l'égard des questions d'éthique Claire DEMIOT, Dominique MALAUZAT

Catégorie VI - Psychologues Sophie LEYMARIE

Catégorie VII - Travailleurs sociaux

Catégorie VIII - Personnes qualifiées en raison de leur compétence en matière juridique Dominique JOUHANNEAUD, Pierre VERGNE, Paolo RASO

Catégorie IX - Représentants des associations agréées de malades et d'usagers du système de santé Norbert VIDAL, Dominique FLOUCAUD

Experts pédiatres : Docteur Rachel FROGET – Professeur Vincent GUIGONIS – Docteur Alexandra MASSON-ROUCHAUD – Docteur Laure PONTHER

Les membres impliqués dans le projet n'ont pas participé à la délibération du 25 mars 2021.

Liste des documents étudiés:

• le courrier de demande d'avis daté et signé du 19 mars 2021

• le formulaire daté et signé de demande d'autorisation auprès de l'ANSM ou de demande d'avis au comité de protection des personnes pour une recherche mentionnée au 1° ou au 2° de l'article L. 1121-1 du code de la sante publique ne portant pas sur un produit mentionné à l'article L. 5311-1 du code de la santé publique daté et signé du 19 mars 2021

• le document additionnel à la demande d'avis au CPP complété daté et signé du 19 mars 2021

Dossier scientifique

• le protocole de recherche version 2.0 du 19/03/2021

• le résumé en français du protocole version 2.0 du 19/03/2021

• le document d'information et formulaire de consentement destiné aux patients version 2.0 du 19/03/2021

• la copie de l'attestation d'assurance du 28 janvier 2021

• l'attestation de l'adéquation des moyens humains, matériels et techniques au projet de recherche et de leur compatibilité avec les impératifs de sécurité des personnes qui s'y prêtent signée et datée du 19 mars 2021

• la liste des centres version 2.0 du 19/03/2021 et *curriculum vitae* correspondant

Les réponses du promoteur déposées sur le SI de la CNRIPH le 2 avril 2021, notifiées ci-dessous, ont été soumises en réunion plénière dématérialisée, le 8 avril 2021.

Liste des documents étudiés:

Dossier administratif

Le courrier de demande d'avis daté et signé

Le formulaire daté et signé de demande d'autorisation auprès de l'ANSM ou de demande d'avis au comité de protection des personnes pour une recherche mentionnée au 1° ou au 2° de l'article L. 1121-1 du code de la sante publique ne portant pas sur un produit mentionné à l'article L. 5311-1 du code de la santé publique

Le document additionnel à la demande d'avis au CPP complété daté et signé

Dossier scientifique

Le protocole de recherche version 3.0 du 2/04/2021

Le résumé en français du protocole version 3.0 du 2/04/2021

Le document d'information et formulaire de consentement destiné aux patients version 3.0 du 2/04/2021

La copie de l'attestation d'assurance

L'attestation de l'adéquation des moyens humains, matériels et techniques au projet de recherche et de leur compatibilité avec les impératifs de sécurité des personnes qui s'y prêtent

La liste des centres version 3.0 du 2/04/2021 et curriculum vitae correspondant

Catégorie I - Personnes qualifiées en matière de recherche biomédicale

Elodie PFENDER

Catégorie I - Personnes qualifiées en matière de biostatistique ou d'épidémiologie

Claire BAHANS

Catégorie II - Médecins généralistes

Philippe NICOT

Catégorie III - Pharmaciens

Marie-Anne de VINZELLES

Catégorie IV - Infirmier(e)s

Catégorie V - Personnes qualifiées en raison de leur compétence à l'égard des questions d'éthique

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Catégorie VIII - Personnes qualifiées en raison de leur compétence en matière juridique

Pierre VERGNE, Paolo RASO

Catégorie IX - Représentants des associations agréées de malades et d'usagers du système de santé

Norbert VIDAL, Dominique FLOUCAUD

Experts pédiatres : Docteur Rachel FROGET – Professeur Vincent GUIGONIS – Docteur Alexandra MASSON-ROUCHAUD – Docteur Laure PONTHER

Les membres impliqués dans le projet ne participent pas à la délibération.

Le Comité de Protection des Personnes du Sud-Ouest et Outre-Mer 4, décide :

Avis Favorable

Cependant, le Comité alerte le Promoteur sur le manque de clarté et de rigueur du dossier soumis.

Pour le CPP SOOMIV,

Claire BAHANS, Présidente du Comité

*Il Comitato Etico di Area Vasta Emilia Centro della Regione Emilia-Romagna (CE-AVEC) è stato istituito presso IRCCS Azienda Ospedaliero – Universitaria di Bologna, Policlinico S.Orsola-Malpighi con delibera n. 6 del 10/1/2018 e rinnovato con delibera n.44 del 09/03/2021.
Il CE-AVEC opera in conformità al DM 12/05/2006 e al DM 08/02/2013.*

Ns riferimento da citare sempre nella corrispondenza

N° 473-2021-SPER-AUSLBO valutato il 20/05/2021

NOTA: per qualsiasi successiva comunicazione relativa allo studio in oggetto è indispensabile fare riferimento al codice interno CE sopra indicato e alla data della seduta di valutazione.

Il presente parere è spedito dal Dr. Corrado Iacono (referente studio). Le comunicazioni in merito a questo parere devono essere inoltrate all'indirizzo corrado.iacono@ausl.bologna.it.

Dr. Daniele Mandrioli

Cooperativa Sociale Istituto
Nazionale Per Lo Studio E Il
Controllo Dei Tumori E Delle
Malattie Ambientali Bernardino
Ramazzini

Direttore Generale

Azienda USL di Bologna – IRCCS
ISNB

Dr.ssa Renata Mesirca

UO Governo Clinico e Sistema
Qualità
Azienda USL di Bologna – IRCCS
ISNB

Oggetto: 473-2021-SPER-AUSLBO – SPRINT- SUSTAINABLE PLANT PROTECTION TRANSITION: A GLOBAL HEALTH APPROACH [TRANSIZIONE VERSO UNA PROTEZIONE DELLE COLTURE SOSTENIBILE: UN APPROCCIO DI SALUTE GLOBALE]

Protocollo: SPRINT CSS

SIRER ID: 2345

Promotore: Cooperativa Sociale Istituto Nazionale Per Lo Studio E Il Controllo Dei Tumori E Delle Malattie Ambientali Bernardino Ramazzini

Sperimentatore principale: Dr. Daniele Mandrioli

Centro sperimentale: Cooperativa Sociale Istituto Nazionale Per Lo Studio E Il Controllo Dei Tumori E Delle Malattie Ambientali Bernardino Ramazzini

Elenco dei documenti esaminati:

- Lettera di intenti, datata 12/04/2021
- Elenco centri
- Parere Comitato Etico coordinatore
- Elenco documenti
- Protocollo, versione 2.0 del 03/2021
- Sinossi, ricevuta il 15/04/2021
- Horizon - Proposal Submission Forms
- Modulistica centro-specifica CE-AVEC

*Comitato Etico di Area Vasta Emilia Centro della Regione Emilia-Romagna
presso IRCCS Azienda Ospedaliero – Universitaria di Bologna, Policlinico S.Orsola-Malpighi
Via Albertoni, 15 – 40138 BOLOGNA*

<http://www.aosp.bo.it/content/comitato-etico>

Per i contatti si rimanda al sito web sopra indicato

Il Comitato Etico di Area Vasta Emilia Centro della Regione Emilia-Romagna (CE-AVEC) è stato istituito presso IRCCS Azienda Ospedaliero – Universitaria di Bologna, Policlinico S.Orsola-Malpighi con delibera n. 6 del 10/1/2018 e rinnovato con delibera n.44 del 09/03/2021. Il CE-AVEC opera in conformità al DM 12/05/2006 e al DM 08/02/2013.

- Foglio informativo, versione 1.0 del 30/03/2021
- Modulo di consenso, versione 2 del 14/05/2021
- Lettera per il MMG
- SPRINT Questionario esposizione e salute
- SPRINT Questionario pesticidi e modalità comunicazione
- SPRINT Questionario azienda e attività agricola
- CV del PI
- Dichiarazione sul conflitto di interessi PI
- Checklist SPIRIT
- Statuto IR-2009

Il Comitato Etico, nella seduta telematica del 20 maggio 2021, esprime all'unanimità parere favorevole alla conduzione dello studio in oggetto.

Lo studio potrà essere avviato solo dopo aver ricevuto il nulla osta da parte della Direzione Generale della struttura sanitaria di riferimento ai sensi dell'art. 7 della L.R. n. 9/2017. Sarà cura dei competenti uffici avviare le pratiche per il suddetto nulla osta.

Si precisa, infine, che:

- ai fini del monitoraggio dell'andamento dello studio in oggetto, lo Sperimentatore Responsabile dovrà comunicare al Comitato Etico le seguenti informazioni relativamente a questo singolo centro sperimentale: data di inizio arruolamento, data di fine arruolamento e data di conclusione dello studio. In ogni caso, a partire dall'anno di approvazione dello studio e fino alla sua conclusione, almeno una volta all'anno e comunque entro e non oltre il 31 dicembre, dovrà essere fornito un rapporto annuale sullo stato di avanzamento dello studio.
- Il modulo per il monitoraggio è disponibile a questo indirizzo: <https://www.aosp.bo.it/content/monitoraggio-degli-studi> e andrà inviato compilato, firmato e datato, esclusivamente in formato elettronico all'indirizzo e-mail dedicato comet.speri@ausl.bologna.it indicando nell'oggetto il nome dello Sperimentatore Responsabile locale ed il codice assegnato dal Comitato allo studio

Cordiali saluti,

IL PRESIDENTE

Allegato: elenco dei componenti del Comitato Etico presenti al momento dell'espressione del presente parere

ODOBRENJE ETIČKOG POVJERENSTVA

Predmet: istraživanje u sklopu projekta

SPRINT - Prijelaz na održivu upotrebu sredstava za zaštitu bilja: globalni pristup zdravlju (engl. Sustainable Plant Protection Transition: a Global Health Approach - SPRINT

Voditelj projekta: prof.dr.Violette Geissen
Glavni istraživač za RH: dr.sc. Igor Pasković
Suradnica u KBC-u Rijeka: prof.dr.sc. Štefica Dvornik

Mjesto istraživanja: KBC Rijeka, Klinički zavod za laboratorijsku dijagnostiku

Pregledani dokumenti:

- Zamolba
- Istraživački protokol
- Suglasnost predstojnice Kliničkog zavoda za laboratorijsku dijagnostiku
- Obavijest za ispitanike
- Suglasnost za sudjelovanje u istraživanju

PROVOĐENJE ISTRAŽIVANJA ODOBRENO
SJEDNICA ODRŽANA: 17. ožujka 2021.

NA SJEDNICI SUDJELOVALI:

prof.dr.sc. Ivan Bubić, dr.med.
izv.prof.prim.dr.sc. Dean Markić, dr.med.
doc.dr.sc. Goran Poropat, dr.med.
prof.dr.sc. Danko Bakarčić, dr.med.dent.
doc.dr.sc. Viviana Avancini-Dobrović, dr.med.

Klasa: 003-05/21-1/35
Ur.broj: 2170-29-02/1-21-2
Rijeka, 17. ožujka 2021.

Etičko povjerenstvo KBC-a Rijeka:
Zamjenik predsjednice Povjerenstva
prof.dr.sc. Ivan Bubić, dr.med.

REPUBLIKA SLOVENIJA
MINISTRSTVO ZA ZDRAVJE

Komisija Republike Slovenije za medicinsko etiko

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Doc. dr. Matjaž Glavan

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Prof. dr. Vita Dolžan, dr. med.

Univerza v Ljubljani, Medicinska fakulteta, Vrazov trg 2, 1000 Ljubljana
vita.dolzan@mf.uni-lj.si

Številka: 0120-146/2021/3

Datum: 12. 5. 2021

Zadeva: Ocena etičnosti predložene raziskave

Zveza: vaša vloga z dne 26. 3. 2021

Spoštovani,

Komisija Republike Slovenije za medicinsko etiko (v nadaljevanju KME RS) je dne 31. 3. 2021 prejela dopolnitev vloge za oceno etičnosti raziskave z naslovom »Prehod v trajnostno zaščito kmetijskih rastlin za ohranjanje globalnega zdravja - Sustainable plant protection transition: a global health approach«.

Namen mednarodne raziskave SPRINT (Univerza Wageningen, Nizozemska), v kateri sodeluje tudi Republika Slovenija je razviti, preizkusiti, potrditi in zagotoviti globalno orodje za oceno zdravstvenega tveganja za celostno oceno vplivov sredstev za varstvo rastlin (formulacije, aktivne snovi, metaboliti in mešanice) na kopenske in vodne ekosisteme, rastline, živali in zdravje ljudi.

Skrbnik in odgovorni raziskovalec, oseba odgovorna za terenske raziskave:

Doc. dr. Matjaž Glavan, univ. dipl. ing. agronomije

Odgovorna oseba za medicinski del raziskave:

Prof. dr. Vita Dolžan, dr. med.

Pričakovati je, da bo raziskava omogočila opredeliti vpliv sredstev za varstvo rastlin na okolje in na zdravstveno stanje ljudi in živali, ter opredelila načine za prehod na trajnostno rabo sredstev za varstvo rastlin. V slovenskem delu raziskave želijo vključiti 12 slovenskih kmetij, kjer gojijo koruzo in kmetom ter njihovim odjemalcem kmetijskih proizvodov (skupaj cca 70 polnoletnih ljudi) enkrat odvzeti urin, blato, nosni bris in kri za preiskavo sledi pesticidov in podobnih snovi za zaščito rastlin, odvzeti pa želijo tudi vzorce prahu z živine, polj in bivališč kmetov. Zbrani zdravstveni podatki bodo vodeni pod šifro, identiteta kmetov bo znana zgolj vodilnemu

raziskovalcu. Dva tedna naj bi kmetje nosili tudi zapestnico, na kateri naj bi se zbirale določene kemikalije za preiskavo. Vsi bodo imeli dostop do tako pridobljenih zdravstvenih izvidov.

KME RS je vašo vlogo obravnavala na seji 20. aprila 2021 in ugotovila, da je vloga popolna ter da je raziskava etično sprejemljiva. S tem vam za njeno izvedbo izdaja svoje soglasje

Pri nadaljnjih dopisih v zvezi z raziskavo se obvezno sklicujte na številko tega dopisa.

S spoštovanjem,

dr. Božidar Voljč, dr. med.
predsednik KME RS

Vročiti:

- naslovníku – po e-pošti

**Posouzení studie „Přechod k udržitelnější ochraně
rostlin s pomocí přístupu celistvého zdraví“
Ethical Assessment of the study „Sustainable Plant
Protection Transition: a Global Health Approach
(SPRINT)“**

Zadavatel: Vědecká rada ELSPAC/CELSPAC

The requesting authority: The Scientific Board of ELSPAC/CELSPAC

Vypracovala: Etická komise ELSPAC/CELSPAC

Prepared by: Ethics Committee of ELSPAC/CELSPAC

Číslo stanoviska: (C)ELSPAC/EK/1/2021

Ref. No: (C)ELSPAC/EK/1/2021

1. Toto stanovisko Etické komise ELSPAC/CELPAC je vydáváno v návaznosti žádosti o posouzení etické a právní stránky studie „Přechod k udržitelnější ochraně rostlin s pomocí přístupu celistvého zdraví“.

2. Etická komise prostudovala protokol studie, posoudila její etickou a právní stránku, zejména se zaměřením na ochranu osobních údajů, ochrany osobnosti a lidské důstojnosti probandů, možnosti jejich svobodného vystoupení ze studie, stejně jako transparentnosti sběru dat, biologických vzorků nebo jednoznačného stanovení výzkumných cílů a metod vedoucích k jejich dosažení.

3. Etická komise ELSPAC shledala, že předkládaná žádost je koncipována jako navazující výzkum v rámci dlouhodobé studie ELSPAC, resp. CELPAC. Z návrhu je zřejmé, že budou dodrženy všechny standardní mechanismy, které jsou ve studiích ELSPAC/CELPAC vyžadovány (zejména interní pravidla obsažená v Opatření ředitelky Centra č. 1/2018 upravující nakládání s osobními údaji CELPAC ohledně sběru biologických vzorků, nakládání s osobními údaji, ochrana mladistvých a zranitelných osob, předávání osobních údajů třetím stranám apod.).

4. Účast probandů ve studii je bezúplatná. Navržená odměna (vouchery) v podobě 1000 Kč není pojímána jako odměna za získání osobních údajů, ale jako náhrada nákladů spojených s účastí ve studii a vyplňování dotazníků.

5. Etická komise neposuzovala etické aspekty pokusů na zvířatech. Ty je možné realizovat za podmínek stanovených zákonem č. 246/1992 Sb., na ochranu zvířat proti týrání, ve znění pozdějších předpisů (zejména, pokud jde o neinvazivní pokusy na zvířatech; invazivní pokusy podléhají schválení zvláštní odbornou komisí).

6. Za základě shora uvedených podmínek se Etická komise ELSPAC rozhodla

udělit **kladné právně-etické** posouzení předkládané studii, co se týče lidských účastníků.

Etická komise ELSPAC projednala a schválila dne: 23.3.2021

1. This assessment of the ELSPAC/CELPAC Ethics Committee is issued following the application for examination of the ethical and legal aspects of the study "*Sustainable Plant Protection Transition: a Global Health Approach*".

2. Ethics Committee examined the study protocol and assessed the ethical and legal aspects of the research. Ethics Committee particularly focused on the privacy protection, protection of personality and human dignity of probands, their possibility of a free withdrawal from the study, as well as the transparency of the collection of data or biological samples. Committee also considered the definition of the research objectives and methods leading to their achievement.

3. ELSPAC Ethics Committee found that submitted application is designed as a follow-up research study within a longitudinal study ELSPAC (respectively CELPAC). From the proposal it is clear that all standard mechanisms which are required in the ELSPAC/CELPAC studies will be satisfied (especially internal rules stipulated in the Regulation of the Director of Center RECETOX No. 1/2018 governing the processing of personal data in CELPAC concerning the collection of biological samples, treatment of personal data, protection of minors and vulnerable persons, processing of personal data by third parties etc.).

4. The participation of probands in the study is free of charge. The proposed reward (vouchers) consisting from the amount of 1000 CZK is not conceived as a reward for obtaining personal data, but as a reimbursement of participation in the study and completion of questionnaires.

5. The Ethics Committee did not assess the ethical aspects of animal experiments. These can be carried out under the conditions laid down by Law No. 246/1992 Coll., as amended, for the protection of animals against cruelty (especially in the case of non-invasive animal experiments; invasive experiments are subject to approval by a special expert commission).

6. Based on these expectations the ELSPAC Ethics Committee grants

a positive legal and ethical assessment on the submitted study as far as human participants are concerned.

The ELSPAC Ethics Committee reviewed and approved on: 23rd March 2021

Doc. JUDr. Pavel Koukal, Ph.D., chair of ELSPAC Ethics Committee

Mgr. Vlastimil Slovák, member

Mgr. Marika Chrápavá, member

Radboudumc

Radboud universitair medisch centrum

Concernstaf Kwaliteit en Veiligheid
Commissie Mensgebonden Onderzoek
Regio Arnhem-Nijmegen

628

Radboudumc
Afdeling Health Evidence
Geert Groteplein 21N
6525 HE NIJMEGEN

Postbus 9101, 6500 HB Nijmegen
Huispost 348
Gebouw tandheekunde
Philips van Leydenlaan 25 (route 348)
T (024) 361 31 54

commissiemensgebondenonderzoek@radboudumc.nl
KvK 41055629/4

Ons Kenmerk
DS/CMO 097

Datum
01 maart 2021

Titel: SPRINT NL Case Study
Dossiernummer: 2020-7248
NL-nummer: NL76296.091.20

Geachte heer Scheepers,

Bijgevoegd treft u aan het positieve oordeel van de CMO Regio Arnhem-Nijmegen over bovengenoemd onderzoek.

Dit betekent dat het onderzoek kan worden uitgevoerd in de centra die in het positieve oordeel worden genoemd nadat de Raden van Bestuur/Directies van die centra daarvoor toestemming hebben verleend.

Indien het voornemen bestaat het onderzoek ook nog in een ander centrum uit te voeren, dan dient aan de CMO Regio Arnhem – Nijmegen een onderzoeksverklaring (zie website www.ccmo.nl) van het betreffende centrum te worden overlegd. De CMO Regio Arnhem-Nijmegen kan vervolgens het positieve oordeel uitbreiden naar het betreffende centrum.

Voorwaarde voor het uitvoeren van een WMO-onderzoek in het Radboudumc is niet alleen het positieve oordeel van de CMO regio Arnhem-Nijmegen (of een andere erkende METC) maar ook de toestemming van de Raad van Bestuur van het Radboudumc. Informatie over de lokale uitvoerbaarheid is gepubliceerd in het [Integraal Kwaliteitssysteem voor Wetenschappelijk Mensgebonden Onderzoek](#).

Radboudumc

Ik vertrouw erop u met dit schrijven van dienst te zijn en namens de commissie wens ik u succes met de uitvoering van het onderzoek.

Met vriendelijke groet,
Namens de CMO Regio Arnhem-Nijmegen

Drs. R.B. Keus, vicevoorzitter

BESLUIT

Primaire beoordeling

NL nummer:	NL76296.091.20	METC nr.	2020-7248
Titel onderzoek:	SPRINT NL Case Study		

Contactgegevens: Radboudumc te Nijmegen, afdeling Health Evidence
Verrichter: European Commission Horizon 2020 Programme

Besluit

De medisch-ethische toetsingscommissie CMO Regio Arnhem-Nijmegen heeft zich, op grond van artikel 2, tweede lid, sub a van de *Wet medisch wetenschappelijk onderzoek met mensen* (WMO), beraden over bovenstaand onderzoeksdossier.

De commissie oordeelt **positief** over het onderzoeksdossier uit te voeren in het volgende centrum:

- Radboudumc te Nijmegen (hoofdonderzoeker: dr. ir. P.T.J. Scheepers)

Documenten

Het oordeel is gebaseerd op de documenten die in [bijlage 1](#) zijn vermeld.

Achtergrond

Op 17 december 2020 is het onderzoeksdossier ter beoordeling bij de commissie ingediend. Daarna heeft de commissie nadere informatie opgevraagd waarop naar tevredenheid is geantwoord.

Met inachtneming van haar reglement is het onderzoeksdossier besproken in de vergadering van 05 januari 2021; zie [bijlage 2](#) voor de bij de beoordeling betrokken commissieleden.

Overwegingen

De commissie is van oordeel dat aan de voorwaarden in artikel 3 van de WMO is voldaan.

De commissie heeft de inhoud van de onderzoeksverklaring van de deelnemende instelling bekeken. Zij heeft geconstateerd dat is voldaan aan de voorwaarden in artikel 3, onderdeel f, van de WMO. De commissie is van oordeel dat in redelijkheid is voldaan aan het bepaalde in artikel 5 WMO.

De commissie is van oordeel dat het onderzoeksprotocol in een toestemmingsprocedure voorziet die overeenstemt met artikel 6, eerste lid, van de WMO.

De commissie is van mening dat is voldaan aan de voorwaarden in artikel 6, vijfde t/m negende lid, van de WMO. De proefpersonen (en/of degenen die mede/in hun plaats bevoegd zijn tot het geven van toestemming voor deelname aan het onderzoek) worden op gepaste, volledige en begrijpelijke wijze schriftelijk over het onderzoek geïnformeerd en over de mogelijkheid om de toestemming te allen tijde in te trekken.

Verzekeringen

Met inachtneming van het bepaalde in artikel 7 WMO heeft de commissie besloten dat de plicht tot het afsluiten van een WMO-proefpersonenverzekering vervalt.

De commissie heeft geconstateerd dat een aansprakelijkheidsverzekering is afgesloten zoals bepaald in artikel 7, negende lid, van de WMO.

Ten slotte wijst de commissie u op de voorwaarden en verplichtingen die in bijlage 3 zijn vermeld.

Hoogachtend,
Namens de CMO Regio Arnhem-Nijmegen

Drs. R.B. Keus, vicevoorzitter

Nijmegen, 01 maart 2021

Beroepsprocedure

Tegen dit besluit kan een belanghebbende op grond van artikel 23 van de WMO binnen zes weken na de dag waarop het besluit is bekend gemaakt, administratief beroep instellen bij de Centrale Commissie Mensgebonden Onderzoek (CCMO). Het beroepschrift dient u te adresseren aan CCMO, Postbus 16302, 2500 BH Den Haag.

Bijlage 1

Documenten:

- A Aanbiedingsbrief d.d. 17 december 2020
Aanbiedingsbrief d.d. 01 februari 2021, in reactie op commissiemail d.d. 11 januari 2021
Aanbiedingsbrief d.d. 17 februari 2021, in reactie op commissiemail d.d. 16 februari 2021
Aanbiedingsbrief d.d. 24 februari 2021, in reactie op commissiemail d.d. 22 februari 2021
- B ABR-formulier, versie 02 d.d. 01 februari 2021
- C Onderzoeksprotocol, versie 1.1 d.d. 28 januari 2021
- E Proefpersoneninformatie, versie 1.1 d.d. 28 januari 2021
Toestemmingsformulier, versie 1.1 d.d. 28 januari 2021
- F Vragenlijst, versie 1.0 d.d. 17 december 2020
- H CV onafhankelijk arts drs. M. Drijver
- I Onderzoeksverklaring van het Radboudumc te Nijmegen, getekend door afdelingshoofd van
de afdeling Health Evidence d.d. 24 februari 2021, inclusief:
CV dr. ir. P.T.J. Scheepers

Bijlage 2

CMO Regio Arnhem-Nijmegen

Bij de beoordeling betrokken commissieleden

Arts/(vice)voorzitter
Kinderarts
Arts
Ethicus
Jurist
Methodoloog
Proefpersonenlid
Verpleegkundige

R. Keus
S. Henriët
F. Abdo
A. Oerlemans
F. van Agt
E. Bronkhorst
W. Harmsen
S. Bossmann

Bijlage 3

Voorwaarden en verplichtingen*

- **geen bezwaar bevoegde instantie [alleen bij geneesmiddelenonderzoek]:**
er kan pas met het onderzoek worden gestart, wanneer eveneens geen bezwaar wordt gemaakt binnen de voorgeschreven termijn door de bevoegde instantie;
- **geldigheid oordeel:**
het positieve oordeel verliest zijn geldigheid als de inclusie van de eerste proefpersoon niet heeft plaatsgevonden binnen twee jaar nadat dit besluit is genomen;
- **amendementen:**
amendementen dienen ter beoordeling aan de CMO Regio Arnhem-Nijmegen te worden voorgelegd;
- **onderzoekscontract:**
voor aanvang van het onderzoek moet een getekend exemplaar van het goedgekeurde onderzoekscontract bij de CMO Regio Arnhem-Nijmegen ter kennisgeving worden ingediend.
- **multicenter onderzoek:**
Indien er in het kader van de uitvoering van multicenteronderzoek onderzoekscontracten worden afgesloten, gaat de CMO Regio Arnhem-Nijmegen ervan uit dat de onderzoekscontracten met de overige Nederlandse centra gelijkkluidend zijn aan het referentiecontract ten aanzien van de twee onderdelen (criteria voortijdige beëindiging en openbaarmaking onderzoeksresultaten) waarover de CMO Regio Arnhem-Nijmegen oordeelt. Wijkt een lokaal onderzoekscontract op de genoemde punten af van het positief beoordeelde referentiecontract, dan moet dit als amendement ter beoordeling aan de CMO Regio Arnhem-Nijmegen worden voorgelegd.
- **startdatum onderzoek:**
de CMO Regio Arnhem-Nijmegen dient op de hoogte te worden gesteld van de definitieve startdatum van het onderzoek. Dat is de datum waarop de inclusie van de eerste proefpersoon plaatsvindt;
- **voortgangsrapportage:**
één jaar na de startdatum, en ieder jaar daaropvolgend, dient de METC op de hoogte te worden gebracht van de voortgang van de studie middels het formulier 'Voortgangsrapportage';
- **geldigheid verzekering:**
in het geval het verzekeringscertificaat tijdens de voortgang van het onderzoek zijn geldigheid verliest, dient aan de CMO Regio Arnhem-Nijmegen tijdig een afschrift van een nieuw geldig certificaat te worden toegestuurd;
- **melding artikel 10:**
indien het onderzoek een verloop neemt dat in noemenswaardige mate voor de proefpersoon ongunstiger is dan in het onderzoeksdossier is voorzien, moet daarvan terstond mededeling worden gedaan aan de CMO Regio Arnhem-Nijmegen met een verzoek tot een nader oordeel;
- **melding SAE's**
SAE's dienen aan de CMO Regio Arnhem-Nijmegen gemeld te worden (raadpleeg de website van de commissie voor de te volgen procedure).
- **melding SUSAR's en jaarlijkse veiligheidsrapportage [alleen bij geneesmiddelenonderzoek]:**
SUSAR's en jaarlijkse veiligheidsrapportage dienen aan de CMO Regio Arnhem-Nijmegen gemeld te worden (raadpleeg de website van de commissie voor de te volgen procedure).

Radboudumc

- **Advies DSMB [alleen indien een DSMB is ingesteld]**
indien een advies van de DSMB niet volledig wordt opgevolgd, dient de CMO Regio Arnhem-Nijmegen het advies met toelichting over het niet (volledig) opvolgen van het advies te ontvangen en toestemming te geven voor voortzetting van het onderzoek;
- **melding (voortijdige) beëindiging:**
(voortijdige) beëindiging van het onderzoek dient, met redenen omkleed, te worden gemeld aan de CMO Regio Arnhem-Nijmegen.
- **eindrapportage:**
de CMO Regio Arnhem-Nijmegen dient op de hoogte te worden gebracht van de resultaten van het onderzoek middels een eindrapport / (gesubmitte) publicatie.

* Termijnen en overige uitleg ten aanzien van de indiening van de verschillende documenten aan de CMO Regio Arnhem-Nijmegen vindt u op de website van de CCMO bij het standaard onderzoeksdossier en de toelichting daarop en onder stap 4 van het Stappenplan toetsing TC

Bijlage 4

Title: SPRINT NL Case Study
Filenummer CMO : 2020-7248

Dear Mr. Scheepers,

The medical ethical reviewing committee CMO Regio Arnhem-Nijmegen has reviewed the above-mentioned research file on the grounds of section 2, paragraph 2, sub a of the Medical Research Involving Human Subjects Act (WMO).

The committee has approved the research file on 01 March 2021.

The decision is based on the documents mentioned in appendix 1 of the original decision written in Dutch.

With kind regards,

On behalf of the CMO Region Arnhem-Nijmegen

Drs. R.B. Keus, vice-chairman

Vivi Schlünssen, Professor
Aarhus Universitet
Institut for Folkesundhed
Bartholins Allé 2
8000 Aarhus C

Endelig godkendelse

Projekt: SPRINT: Bæredygtige plantebeskyttelsesmidler og deres effekter på økosystemer, planter, dyr og mennesker / SPRINT: Sustainable plant protection products and their effects on ecosystems, plants, animals and humans.

Dato 03-05-2021
Sagsbehandler Anne-Marie Eybye
komite@rm.dk
Tel. +4578410184
Sagsnr. 1-10-72-47-21

De Videnskabetiske Komitéer for Region Midtjylland, Komité I, bekræfter modtagelsen af mail af 3. maj 2021 som svar på komitéens afgørelse af 29. april 2021, hvori der opstilledes betingelser for godkendelsen af projektet.

Side 1

Afgørelse:

Afgørelsen er truffet efter lovbekendtgørelse nr. 1338 af 1. september 2020 om videnskabetisk behandling af sundhedsvidenskabelige forskningsprojekter og sundhedsdatavidenskabelige forskningsprojekter.

Betingelserne for godkendelsen anses for opfyldt. Projektet er hermed endeligt godkendt.

Godkendelsen gælder for de anmeldte forsøgssteder og den anmeldte forsøgsansvarlige i Danmark.

Godkendelsen gælder til den 31. december 2026 og omfatter følgende dokumenter:

- Forsøgsprotokol, version 3, dateret 29. april 2021, fremsendt med mail af 3. maj 2021.
- Mail/brev til landmænd med henblik på rekruttering af forsøgspersoner, version 1, dateret 13. april 2021, fremsendt med mail af 14. april 2021.
- Mail/brev til naboer med henblik på rekruttering af forsøgspersoner, version 1, dateret 13. april 2021, fremsendt med mail af 14. april 2021.

- Mail/brev til familier i nærområdet med henblik på rekruttering af forsøgspersoner, version 1, dateret 13. april 2021, fremsendt med mail af 14. april 2021.
- Brochure med henblik på rekruttering af forsøgspersoner, version og dato ikke angivet, fil navngivet version1_12.02.2021, fremsendt med mail af 12. februar 2021.
- Deltagerinformation, version 3, dateret 29. april 2021, fremsendt med mail af 3. maj 2021.
- Samtykkeerklæring (S3), version 1, dateret 12. februar 2021, fremsendt med mail af 12. februar 2021.
- Spørgeskemaer fremsendt med mail af 12. februar 2021 er godkendt til brug i projektet.

Det bemærkes, at komitéen ikke er ressortmyndighed vedr. regelsættet om databeskyttelse, og at komiteen forudsætter, at projektets indhold vedr. dette er i overensstemmelse med Europa-Parlamentets og Rådets forordning nr. 2016/679 af 27. april 2016 om beskyttelse af fysiske personer i forbindelse med behandling af personoplysninger og om fri udveksling af sådanne oplysninger og databeskyttelsesloven.

Iværksættelse af projektet i strid med godkendelsen kan straffes med bøde eller fængsel, jf. komitélovens § 41.

Ændringer:

Foretages der væsentlige ændringer i protokolmateriale under gennemførelsen af projektet, skal disse anmeldes til komitéen i form af tillægsprotokoller. Ændringerne må først iværksættes efter godkendelse fra komitéen, jf. komitélovens § 27, stk. 1.

Anmeldelse af tillægsprotokoller skal ske elektronisk på www.drvk.dk med det allerede tildelte anmeldelsesnummer og adgangskode.

Væsentlige ændringer er bl.a. ændringer, der kan få betydning for forsøgspersonernes sikkerhed, fortolkning af den videnskabelige dokumentation, som projektet bygger på samt gennemførelsen eller ledelsen af projektet. Det kan fx være ændringer i in- og eksklusionskriterier, forsøgsdesign, antal forsøgspersoner, projektførelse, forsøgsprocedurer, behandlingsvarighed, effektparametre, ændringer om de forsøgsansvarlige eller forsøgssteder samt indholdsmæssige ændringer i det skriftlige informationsmateriale til forsøgspersonerne.

Hvor nye oplysninger betyder, at forskeren overvejer at ændre proceduren eller stoppe forsøget, skal komitéen orienteres om det.

Bivirkninger og hændelser:

Løbende indberetning

Komitéen skal omgående underrettes, hvis der under projektet optræder formodet alvorlige, uventede bivirkninger eller alvorlige hændelser, jf. komitélovens § 30, stk. 1.

Indberetningen skal ledsages af kommentarer om eventuelle konsekvenser for forsøget. Det er kun bivirkninger og hændelser forekommet i Danmark, der skal indberettes. Underretning skal ske senest 7 dage efter, at sponsor eller den forsøgsansvarlige har fået kendskab til tilfældet.

Ved indberetning kan anvendes et skema, der findes på www.nvk.dk. Skemaet med evt. bilag skal indsendes elektronisk i pdf-format til komite@rm.dk.

Årlig indberetning

Én gang årligt i hele forsøgsperioden skal komitéen have tilsendt en liste over alle formodet alvorlige (ventede og uventede) bivirkninger og alvorlige hændelser, som er indtruffet i forsøgsperioden sammen med en rapport om forsøgspersonernes sikkerhed, jf. komitélovens § 30, stk. 2. Har der ikke været alvorlige bivirkninger og hændelser skal dette ligeledes indberettes.

Ved indberetning kan anvendes et skema, der findes på www.nvk.dk. Skemaet med evt. bilag skal indsendes elektronisk i pdf-format til komite@rm.dk.

Afslutning:

Den forsøgsansvarlige skal senest 90 dage efter afslutningen af projektet underrette komitéen herom, jf. komitélovens § 31, stk. 1. Projektet regnes som afsluttet, når indsamling af data er afsluttet.

Afbrydes projektet tidligere end planlagt, skal en begrundelse herfor sendes til komitéen senest 15 dage efter, at beslutningen er truffet, jf. komitélovens § 31, stk. 2.

Hvis projektet ikke påbegyndes, skal dette samt årsagen hertil meddeles komitéen.

Komitéen beder om kopi af den afsluttende forskningsrapport eller publikation, jf. komitélovens § 28, stk. 2. Vi skal i den forbindelse gøre opmærksom på, at der er pligt til at offentliggøre både negative, positive og inkonklusive forsøgsresultater, jf. komitélovens § 20, stk. 1, nr. 8.

Tilsyn:

Komitéen fører tilsyn med, at projektet udføres i overensstemmelse med godkendelsen, jf. komitélovens § 28 og § 29.

Venlig hilsen

Anne-Marie Eybye
Sekretær

midt
regionmidtjylland

Side 4

Kopi til:

- Postdoc Anne Vested, Aarhus Universitet

UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL
DE MAR DEL PLATA

Mar del Plata 27 de mayo de 2021

Dra. Virginia Aparicio
INTA EEA/Facultad de Ciencias Agrarias
UNMdP

El Comité de Ética de la Investigación del Programa Temático Interdisciplinario en Bioética (PTIB) dependiente de la Secretaría de Ciencia y Tecnología de la Universidad Nacional de Mar del Plata, deja constancia que, habiendo realizado el Análisis Bioético del Proyecto de Investigación titulado: “Transición de protección vegetal sostenible: un enfoque de salud global” de la Dra. Virginia Aparicio. INTA EEA/Facultad de Ciencias Agrarias de la Universidad Nacional de Mar del Plata, **no encuentra objeciones éticas para su ejecución, por lo que el mismo se encuentra Aprobado** con fecha 27 de mayo de 2021.

Este Comité de Ética de la Investigación del PTIB se encuentra inscripto en el Registro Provincial de Comités de Ética en Investigación, dependiente del Comité de Ética Central en Investigación -Ministerio de Salud de la Provincia de Buenos Aires- con fecha 30/12/2016, bajo el N° 061/2016, Folio 124, Libro N° 2. Reacreditado en el mes de diciembre de 2019.

Aclaración: se transfiere a los centros especializados que aprobarán el Proyecto de Investigación, la responsabilidad de la pertinencia y cientificidad del estudio, ya que el Análisis Bioético los presupone y se funda en ellos.

Comité de Ética de la Investigación
Programa Temático Interdisciplinario en Bioética
Secretaría de Ciencia y Tecnología
Universidad Nacional de Mar del Plata